

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF RESOURCE-CONSTRAINED IOT ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a transformative approach that connects objects (things) of various natures with sensing, computing and communication capabilities. These objects are characterized by small size, less computing power, less memory and limited battery. This article first discusses the basic concepts of the Internet of Things and the hardware and software platforms needed to realize IoT environments.

Keywords: Internet of things, intelligent environment, limited resource, RDF, Hydra platform, A3-TAG platform, CoCaMAAL model.

One of the main results of the activities of creative, social and intellectual people is the creation of information resources to preserve them for future generations to use. It is no exaggeration to say that the level of development of the use of previously collected information and information protection technologies throughout the history of mankind has had a significant impact on the development of productive forces. The loss of information causes civilization to be pushed back centuries. However, in order to effectively use previously collected data, special tools and technologies are needed, with the help of which special methods for working with information can be implemented [17].

The Internet of Things (or briefly IoT) is a network environment in which arbitrary objects, whether human or animal, each have a unique identifier and can transmit information over the network. No human-human or human-computer interaction is needed for this information exchange. The Internet of Things is created by bringing together wireless networking technologies, micro-electronic systems and the Internet.

In the Internet of Things, an object is a pacemaker connected to a human heart, biological chips connected to animals and acting as a transmitter, a vehicle

equipped with sensors and an on-board computer, or any human-made device with an IP address that can transmit information over a network. From this point of view, the concept of the Internet of things is understood mostly as device-to-device communication. Such relationships are widely used in the production of energy, oil and gas. Products with built-in device-device relationships are called smart (or intelligent) products. In short, we can understand the "internet of things" as the communication of smart devices.

In today's era, IoT technology has spread widely, from small appliances to big cities. Big data created here is widely used in the creation of other technological innovations. [3], [22], [20], [2]

A modern trend in IoT technologies is cloud computing, where computing is (partially) moved from the global cloud to localized environments (Internet periphery) using routers or gateways [9]. Most of the research conducted in this field is devoted to the collection and transmission of information from devices to gateways, its subsequent integration and sending to the cloud. Using the IP concept, it is possible to involve the devices in the environment in collaborative computing to build and provide information services. Separately,

resource-constrained IoT environments [19] are selected, which are characterized not by the number of participating SNGs, but by their heterogeneity and the variety of communication paths between them. The resource-constrained nature of such environments involves the use of limited communication networks (low data transfer rates) and SSC with limited computing resources [18].

As an example of an intelligent environment application deployed in a resource-constrained IoT environment, consider a portable version of a collaborative event system to be organized indoors. [5], [21]. Example 1. ("Joint Action System"). This system we are considering can be used for conferences, meetings, lectures, etc. this category is intended for information support in the conduct of public events (Figure 1.). For the

conference mode, software agents are allocated that implement the basic services for managing the conference, the program of the event, presentations of speakers and content. The computing environment of the system is localized in a room (eg, a conference room) equipped with computing and media equipment. To connect the main agents (participants) to the conference, it is possible to use other existing network computing devices (router, projector, etc.) instead of a traditional personal computer. Two projectors and screens can be installed in the room: one shows the speaker's slides, the other shows the program of the event. Many conference participants use a personal mobile network computing device (smartphones, tablets) working with a client agent to participate in the conference.

Figure 1. Architecture of the joint activities management system

There are various platforms for creating an intellectual space from the room (classroom) under review. Some of these platforms use distributed content provided by the Resource Description Framework (RDF) model to exchange information between agents. The JTangPS platform [6] implements a publish/subscribe model where tracked events are represented as an RDF graph. Presentation and inference mechanisms are used to search and interpret event materials. Users (agents) join the event by comparing templates in RDF graphs. An ontology-oriented approach is used to create a publish/subscribe model-based intellectual environment system. Here, the language understood by the subscriber (agent) and the ontological representation of events are used (the event is converted from the issuing agent into an RDF triple and delivered to the subscriber). According to the structure of events, systems

are divided into two groups: image-based (many attribute/value pairs) and XML-based. Some researchers [14] present the infrastructure of the system as a "semantic knowledge space" to create an intellectual space. A special RDF data query language (RDQL) is used for knowledge query. Also, the platforms we have described are not designed to deploy intelligent space in the resource-constrained IoT environments that are currently in widespread use on the Internet. These platforms focus on traditional PCs (desktops, laptops) without supporting the existing variety of network computing devices in IoT-environments.

[12], [11], [10] and other sources reviewed various platforms that can be used to create an intelligent space in the IoT environment. It is concluded that platforms based on intellectual spaces are classified as event-oriented, service-oriented, virtual, multi-agent, multi-agent classes.

The Hydra platform [15] allows creating an intellectual space based on service-oriented architecture. The Hydra Platform is an open source model platform built for the purpose of information management in computer networks. Facilitates the creation of complex resource network models by providing a consistent storage facility for network topology and associated datasets. The Hydra Platform is built around a server that provides all functionality as a web service to which applications can connect to access data. This platform is composed of separate modules to manage the context and security of services, events, devices, information storage. Semantic, service, network levels and security levels are distinguished between these modules. The platform supports dynamic reconfiguration and self-protection.

A3-TAG platform [16] creates a smart space based on the shared space of tuples. Many participants exchange information through this space. To enable the operation of a large number of devices in the platform, devices are combined into groups and further interaction is carried out between groups of devices.

From the point of view of ke, our platforms are used to create specific IoT environments - Wireless sensor network (WSN), which in turn do not allow creating an intelligent space for a wide variety of existing IoT circles.

Some classes of IoT environments are formed by platforms that support a wide variety of network computing devices, but are limited in their scope of application. An example of such platforms is the CoCaMAAL platform. The CoCaMAAL platform represents a class of intelligent space for helping people in everyday life based on cloud technologies. By collecting data from many sensors and storing it in the cloud, the platform allows various applications to organize access to this information to build and provide information services. There is significant complexity in managing sensor data and retrieving personal data, as well as monitoring user activities and deploying relevant situational services. The CoCaMAAL model tries to solve such problems and implement a service-oriented architecture (SOA) to create a unified context. This is done by efficiently collecting raw sensor data and selecting relevant services in a timely manner using a context management system (CMS). Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) services are improved with a unified model that integrates patients, devices, computing servers into a single virtual community [1].

In an article titled "meSchup: A Platform for Programming Interconnected Smart Things," published in the November 2017 issue of *Computer*, the researchers describe an abstraction layer and a web-based integrated programming environment. "Developing software for the Internet of Things, programming the world around us, and creating innovative applications that affect our daily lives are big challenges. Current programming approaches, best practices, development environments, and tools are insufficient to efficiently support a network of managed smart devices. We believe it is important to build on existing skills (such as web development) and use online infrastructures (such as web-based IDEs) to lower the barrier to entry" [23].

Promising for creating intelligent space in various resource-limited IoT environments is the popular M3 Architecture, especially implemented in the form of the smart-M3 technology platform. The M3 architecture

supports the concept of Smart Spaces with the localization and interaction of existing resources, their semantics and information-based programming on this dynamic knowledge store (in the form of a semantic network). The M3 architecture was originally defined by a consortium participating in the SOFIA project (Smart Objects for Smart Applications) funded by Artemis JU and the Finnish nationally funded DIEM (Device Interoperability Ecosystem) program working in strong collaboration with Nokia Corporation. M3 stands for Multi-device, Multi-vendor and Multi-domain. [8].

Broker RedSIB is a platform designed for use on personal computers and offers an improved subscription processing algorithm. RedSIB is an evolution of the original Smart-M3 SIB implementation. The Redland library is used to maintain a triplestore and SPARQL support. The subscription mechanism has been redesigned for better performance. RedSIB (also Smart-M3 SIB) consists of two subsystems (sib-daemon and sib-tcp). D-BUS communication system is used for data exchange between these subsystems. Since D-BUS is not designed to transfer large amounts of data, the efficiency is mainly reduced. [13] authors present an OSGi SIB broker aimed at deployment in IoT environments with support for the Java language. Based on the OSGi platform, the broker is modular and extensible, which allows it to add new functionality. The PySIB broker implementation provides a "light-weight" modular broker designed to run on a resource-constrained Python-enabled network computing device. At the same time, existing applications of these brokers have the status of research prototypes, which do not emphasize practically important features, such as customization, fault tolerance, and unitary programming capabilities, especially for the available resources of the IoT environment.

The diversity of existing platforms and systems for organizing the intelligent space is related to the hardware-network diversity of IoT environments themselves. The implementation of existing data warehouses is designed only for a narrow class of IoT environments. Thus, in the conditions of the diversity of the IoT-environment, the problem arises that the information service from one intellectual space cannot be transferred or integrated into the intellectual space of another IoT environment.

Another issue is the volatility of IoT environments and the dynamics of involving networked computing devices. Instability manifests itself in periodic interruptions (breaks) of the network connection between data storage and software agents. The number of participants (in the form of network computing devices) changes dynamically: mobile network computing devices can join (enter the environment) and disconnect (leave the environment). Thus, in the conditions of instability and dynamics of the IoT environment, the problem of various failures related to both data storage and software agents arises. The presence of a problem prevents the establishment and delivery of the service, which leads to the need to perform failure recovery while orchestrating the interactions of the agents. [7].

The diversity of IoT among existing applications of information warehousing has led to the emergence of different ways of programming the interaction of agents necessary for the co-construction of an information service. Due to the flexibility of the ontology-oriented representation of the content of the data store,

the methods of programming interaction when using a data store can also differ. Thus, in the context of different ways of interaction of programming, there are problems of integration of information services or the transfer of a service from one intellectual environment to another, which leads to the need to implement different methods of interaction between agents to support integration or transfer [4].

The above-mentioned problems related to the diversity, instability and dynamics of IoT environments have not been fully resolved in the existing platforms. The solution of these problems is possible at the level of the software infrastructure of the intellectual space, which includes information storage and software agents. Thus, it is necessary to create an infrastructure of such smart mwhits that will support various IoT environments as well as provide resilience to failures in the face of environment diversity, instability and dynamics.

RESULT

The article considers the problems of deploying intellectual space in IoT environments limited by intellectual spaces and resources. The definition of the software infrastructure of the intellectual space and its main tasks and platforms for organizing the activities of services in the intellectual space are considered.

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